

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program to Synchronize the Non-Verbal Social Communication Skills among ASD-Children in Pakistani Context

Hina Hadayat Ali, Hina Fazil

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Abstract

The study aimed to measure the effectiveness of implementing the DTT program to synchronize non-verbal social communication skills among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan. Children with ASD were taken as the population of the study. Two children diagnosed with ASD enrolled at Govt. The study participants were taken by the Special Education Centre, Gojra, district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province. The single-subject study design was employed to get answers to the research questions. The analysis of baseline data to intervention data contrast was the most authentic presentation of intervention effect in a single-subject study design (Vannest et al., 2013). The current research evaluated the effect of DTT intervention on non-verbal social communication skills acquisition and correct/independent responding by each chosen subject of the study under each given trial through Tau-U.

Introduction

Discrete Trial Training (DTT) is beneficial to deal with different non-verbal social communication skills deficits among children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Social interaction/social greetings were developed by various researchers, e.g. (Hendrickson et al., 1982; Nientimp and Cole, 1992; Zanolli and Daggett 1998; Stevenson, 2000; Garfinkle and Schwartz, 2002; Whalen et al., 2006; Carr, 2007; Schrandt, 2009; Yun et al., 2014; Tzanakaki et al., 2014; Garcia-Albea, 2014; Groskreutz, 2015; and Hood, 2015).

Understanding/recognition/using effect was developed by different researchers, e.g. (Gena, 2005; DeQuinzio, 2007; Downs and Strand, 2008; Kouo and Egel, 2016; and Walker, 2017). The skill of Gestures was developed by different researchers, e.g. (Buffington, 1998; Ingersoll et al., 2007; and Waldvogel et al., n.d.). Coordinated/integrated .g.e ,srehcraeser tnerreffid yb depoleved saw noitacinummoc labrev-non 20 ,la te aneG) .g.e ,noisserpxe laicaf fo noitceted eht depoleved srehcraeser suoiraV .(2018 ,nadmaH)05; and DeQuinzio, 2007). Different researchers developed the sharing of interests, e.g. (Marzullo-Kerth et al., 2011). Various researchers developed the sharing of emotions, e.g. (Ghezzi, 2007). Above mentioned literature leaves a gap to measure the effectiveness of implementing the DTT program to synchronize non-verbal social communication skills among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan.

Undoubtedly, DTT has been successfully researched constantly across the world throughout the last forty-eight years but is still not being used as a genuinely valid option for developing non-verbal social communication skills for children with ASD in Pakistan. This is primarily because the researchers have not researched the area. Due to this, this teaching strategy is underused. In addition, there are presently few available options to teach various non-verbal social communication skills to children diagnosed with ASD in Pakistan. Simultaneously, adequate research does not support the efficacy of these options.

A brief review of research studies conducted on ASD in Pakistan is presented here. Azeem and Imran (2007) surveyed the assessment and management of children with ASD. Suhail and Zafar (2008) found the prevalence of autism in special education schools of Lahore. Imran et al. (2011) studied autism knowledge and attitudes among healthcare professionals in Lahore, Pakistan. Mahmood (2012) designed video games and interactive applications to enhance learning in children with ASD. Tahir et al. (2013) studied the challenges in requirements engineering for mobile applications for disabled/autism. Imran and Azeem (2014) worked on the perspective of ASD from Pakistan. Fazil and Suleman (2014) investigated school administrators' perceptions about facilities available in schools for children with autism in Pakistan. Ahmad and Shahid (2015) designed and evaluated mobile learning applications for autistic children in

Pakistan. Sharmin et al. (2018) informed about autism support innovative technology design. Akhter et al. (2018) conducted a survey on integrating therapies in autistic children based in Karachi, Pakistan. Khowaja and Salim (2019) conducted an experimental evaluation on serious game for children with autism to learn vocabulary. Above mentioned nature and status of research leaves another strong gap to measure the effectiveness of implementing the DTT program to synchronize non-verbal social communication skills among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan.

As one of the leading teaching options used to teach non-verbal social communication skills in a controlled and systematic way among children with ASD across the world, DTT paves the way for its implementation with the ASD segment of the population for developing non-verbal social communication skills in Pakistan as well. Therefore, DTT has been planned to serve the children who have non-verbal social communication skills deficits by the researchers which allowed the said children a way to maximize the chances of developing non-verbal social communication skills by teaching in simplified instructions with facile steps which enabled them: 1) how to comprehend; and 2) how to produce socially appropriate language for proper and effective interpersonal communication in their particular surroundings.

In the light of the above-stated need, the researchers have planned to use a structured series of learning trials to develop non-verbal social communication skills among children with ASD with the following steps: 1) an instruction; 2) a prompt; 3) a response; 4) a consequence; 5) an inter-trial interval under the format of DTT. This sequence was then repeated to provide maximum opportunities to practice and strengthen the formulated skill on providing immediate positive reinforcement to reach the desired outcome of the current study (Smith, 2001). Therefore, the study aimed to measure the effectiveness of implementing the DTT program to synchronize non-verbal social communication skills among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan. Finally, the researchers formulated the following research questions to answer by keeping the aim of the study in mind:

1. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of sustained eye contact among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
2. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of coordinating eye contact with vocal response among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
3. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of coordinating eye contact with wait to verbal respond among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
4. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using happy facial expressions among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
5. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
6. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of pointing the picture among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?
7. What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of showing the picture among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Methodology

Population

Children with ASD were taken as the population of the study.

Biographical Details of the Participants

Two children diagnosed with ASD enrolled at Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra, district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province were taken as the participants of the study. PA (a pseudonym) was enrolled at Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra. She was a girl of fifteen years and eight months old. She was an adolescent girl. Her order in siblings was third. She had no sibling with a disability in the family. She belonged to a middle social class with a family income of thirty-five thousand per month. Her religion was Islam. PB (a pseudonym) was enrolled at Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra. She was a girl of nine years and two months old. She was a middle childhood girl. Her order in siblings was fourth. She had no sibling with a disability in the family. She belonged to a working social class with a family income of thirty fifteen thousand per month. Her religion was Islam.

Assigned Tasks

PA had eye contact as a significant area of deficit observed on the diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders,

5th edition. Therefore, the researchers intended to synchronize the following skills in her repertoire:

1. The skill of sustained eye contact
2. The skill of coordinating eye contact with vocal respond
3. The skill of coordinating eye contact with wait to verbal respond

PB had affect and gestures as a major area of deficit observed on the diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders, 5th edition. Therefore, the researchers intended to synchronize the following skills in her repertoire:

1. The skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions
2. The skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions
3. The skill of pointing the picture
4. The skill of showing the picture

Research Design

The single-subject study design was employed to get answers to the research questions.

Research Instruments

The researchers designed DTT record-keeping sheets. These record-keeping sheets were validated by five experts of the field included: 1) baseline datasheets, 2) treatment datasheets, 3) return to baseline datasheets, 4) first follow up datasheets, and 5) second follow up data sheets based on the 'Module: Discrete Trial Training' developed by National Professional Development Center on Autism Spectrum Disorders in 2010' to collect data and hence statistically analyzed.

The procedure of the Study

At first, the researchers obtained permission from the headmistress of the Govt. Special Education Centre, Gojra, district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province Pakistan, conducted an experimental study there. Second, the researchers obtained parental consent. A third, the researchers collected data across baseline phase, treatment phases, first follow up and second follow up. In the end, the researchers analyzed the obtained data to get answers to the research questions. Data were systematically collected based on the following plan:

1. The total number of DTT sessions was 3, with a maximum of 30 trials in each experimental session for each participant in a day. This way, 900 DTT sessions were conducted, spreading over two months of the training program. From which, each participant observed a total of 180 DTT sessions. Each experimental session was 24 minutes, while each DTT session was expanded over 4 minutes of duration. Each participant was given a break of 1 minute after each DTT session. In this way, 5 minutes of duration were allocated to each DTT session to conduct. There were 3 minutes break within each experimental session for each DTT session. The break was of 6 minutes between each DTT session for each participant. In this way, the total time for each DTT session was 5 minutes, with a total of 75 minutes each day, while the total of 4500 minutes was spreading over two months of training.
2. The conditions or independent variables under which participant A (PA) was required to respond are listed below in table 1. The conditions or independent variable under which participant B (PB) was required to respond are listed below in table 2. A mastery criterion across each step to be achieved was set at 90%.

Table 1

Conditions across Phases in which PA was required to respond

Phases	Description
A	Baseline (investigating initial proficiency level)
B	Administering treatment inside the classroom context under no error correction/signaling no technique (participant with the researcher)
C	Administering treatment inside the classroom context under error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (participant with the researcher)
D	Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under no error correction/signaling no technique (temporarily designed context) (participant with the researcher)
E	Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (temporarily designed context) (participant with the researcher)
A	Return to baseline (withdrawing treatment conditions) (participant with the researcher)
Follow up 1 (appropriateness)	Investigating appropriateness of the skill under novel stimuli (participant with the researcher)
Follow up 2 (generalization)	Generalization of the skill (participant with the class teacher)

Note. This table shows conditions across phases in which PA was required to respond.

Table 2
Conditions across Phases in which PB was required to respond

Phases	Description
A	Baseline (investigating initial proficiency level)
B	Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under regressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to no error correction/signaling no technique (temporarily designed context) (participant with the researcher)
C	Administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under progressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (temporarily designed context) (participant with the researcher)
D	Administering treatment inside the classroom context under regressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to no error correction/signaling no technique (participant with the researcher)
E	Administering treatment inside the classroom context under progressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (participant with the researcher)
A	Return to baseline (withdrawing treatment conditions) (participant with the researcher)
Follow up 1 (appropriateness)	Investigating appropriateness of the skill under novel stimuli (participant with the researcher)
Follow up 2 (generalization)	Generalization of the skill (participant with the class teacher)

Note. This table shows conditions across phases in which PB was required to respond.

3. Intended communication skills to be synchronized under one core area of deficit i.e.

PA's impaired eye contact included: 1) sustained eye contact, 2) coordinating eye contact with the vocal response, and 3) coordinating eye contact with the wait to verbal responses. Intended communication skills to be synchronized under two core areas of deficit, i.e., impaired recognition and detection of facial expressions and impaired recognizing/understanding/using the effect of PB included: 1) recognizing/understanding and using happy facial expressions, 2) recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions, 3) pointing the picture, and 4) showing the picture.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis of baseline data to intervention data contrast was the most authentic presentation of intervention effect in a single-subject study design (Vannest et al., 2013). The current research evaluated the effect of DTT intervention on non-verbal social communication skills acquisition and correct/independent responding by each chosen subject of the study under each given trial through Tau-*U*. Tau-*U*, a nonparametric single case effect size, was calculated to determine the magnitude of the DTT intervention effect. It enabled the researcher to investigate: a) within-each phase trend; and b) across each phase existed differences (Brossart et al., 2018). Effect size 0.93 and above was interpreted as solid effective of DTT treatment; effect size falling under 0.66 to 0.92 was indicated as the moderate effect of DTT treatment, effect size ranging 0.50 to 0.65 was represented as the debatable effect of DTT treatment, and less than 0.50 scores were considered as no efficacy of the DTT treatment (Parker and Vannest, 2009) generally in Pakistani society and specifically at Toba Tek Singh District, calculated through the percentage of non-overlapping DTT data within-subjects (Parker and Vannest, 2009), a more scientific way of measuring treatment effect of DTT over visual analysis for synthesizing the obtained data and finally reporting the findings of the study (Parker et al., 2007).

Results

Tau-U analysis was run to inquire the effect size of the executed intervention. The following tables show the effect size of the executed intervention across each targeted non-verbal social communication skill to be synchronized for each study participant.

Table 3

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Sustained Eye Contact across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.691	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.175$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.812	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.176$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.773	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.179$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.814	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.175$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.833	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.175$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.833	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.175$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.830	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.176$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the skill of sustained eye contact.

Table 4

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Coordinating Eye Contact with Vocal Respond across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.812	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.176$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.845	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.169$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.796	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.178$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.855	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.168$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.839	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.172$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.833	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.175$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.839	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.172$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the coordination of eye contact with the vocal response.

Table 5

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Coordinate Eye Contact with Wait to Verbal Respond across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.775	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.179$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.877	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.177$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.829	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.173$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.800	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.160$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.839	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.172$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.851	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.166$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.845	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.169$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the skill of coordinating eye contact with the wait to verbal responses.

Table 6

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Recognizing/Understanding and Using Happy Facial Expressions across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.787	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.178$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.873	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.160$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.800	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.177$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.877	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.163$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.842	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.171$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.854	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.164$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.861	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.161$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using happy facial expressions.

Table 7

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Recognizing/Understanding and Using Angry Facial Expressions across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.764	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.179$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.832	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.155$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.806	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.174$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.892	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.155$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.848	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.168$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.870	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.156$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.857	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.163$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions.

Table 8

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Pointing the Picture across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.816	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.174$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.842	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.164$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.819	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.173$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.862	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.171$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.851	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.166$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.845	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.169$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.848	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.168$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the skill of pointing the picture.

Table 9

Measuring the Effectiveness of Implementing Discrete Trial Training Program for Synchronizing the Skill of Showing the Picture across Experimental Sessions and Follow up Periods under Tau-U Analysis

Baseline Trend		Effect Size	
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.791	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.177$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.842	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.171$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.827	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.174$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.859	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.166$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.848	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.168$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.851	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.166$)
Tau = 0.000	$p = 1.000$	Tau = 0.864	$p = 0.000$ ($SE_{\text{Tau}} = 0.159$)

Note. This table shows baseline trend and effect size across synchronizing the picture's skill.

Discussion

Children with ASD have deficits in interacting and communicating with others as defined in the diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5, 2013). However, as a result of the DTT program, the participants in this research developed various appropriate non-verbal social communication skills. The DTT program provided maximum opportunities to develop these skills. All the participants showed interest in the materials and procedures to learn these skills. Consequently, the study's findings revealed distinctive skill development in the form of a greater number of correct responses until reaching mastery criteria. The researchers discussed the study's findings across two stages: 1) answers to the research questions; and 2) findings of the study from the perspective of literature.

Answers to the Research Questions

Question 1: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of sustained eye contact among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured tau=0.00 significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured tau=0.691 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; tau=0.812 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; tau=0.773 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; tau=0.814 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; tau=0.833 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; tau=0.833 significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and tau 0.830

significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of sustained eye contact.

Question 2: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of coordinating eye contact with vocal response among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.812$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.845$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.796$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.855$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.839$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.833$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.839$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of coordinating eye contact with vocal response.

Question 3: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the coordination of eye contact with wait to verbal responses among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.775$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.800$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.829$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.877$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.839$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.851$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.845$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of coordinate eye contact with the wait to verbal responses.

Question 4: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using happy facial expressions among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.787$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.877$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.800$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.873$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.842$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.854$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.861$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using happy facial expressions.

Question 5: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.764$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.892$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.806$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.892$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.848$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.870$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.857$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of recognizing/understanding and using angry facial expressions.

Question 6: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of pointing the picture among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.816$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.862$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.819$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.842$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.851$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.845$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.848$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of pointing the picture.

Question 7: What is the effectiveness of implementing the discrete trial training program for synchronizing the skill of showing the picture among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan?

Answer: The researchers measured $\tau=0.00$ significant at $p=1.000$ across the baseline phase. Likewise, the researchers measured $\tau=0.791$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across B phase; $\tau=0.842$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across C phase; $\tau=0.827$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across D phase; $\tau=0.859$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across E phase; $\tau=0.848$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across A phase; $\tau=0.851$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F1 phase and $\tau=0.864$ significant at $p=0.000$ with medium to high size effect across F2 phase across synchronizing the skill of showing the picture.

Findings of the Study in the Perspective of Literature

The development of non-verbal social communication skills was generally supported by the findings of research studies e.g. (Hendrickson et al., 1982; Nientimp and Cole, 1992; Zanolli and Daggett 1998; Buffington, 1998; Stevenson, 2000; Garfinkle and Schwartz, 2002; Devlin and Harber 2004; Gena, 2005; Martins and Harris, 2006; Jones et al., 2006; Kasari, 2006; Whalen et al., 2006; Carr, 2007; Lafasakis and Sturmey, 2007; Rocha et al., 2007; DeQuinzio, 2007; Ghezzi, 2007; Ingersoll et al., 2007; Jennett et al., 2008; Downs and Strand, 2008; Miles and Wilder et al., 2009; Schrandt, 2009; Mosier, 2011; Nosik and Williams, 2011; Marzullo-Kerth et al., 2011; Lerman, 2013; Nosik et al., 2013; Carbone et al., 2013; Krstovska-Guerrero and Jones, 2013; Shillingsburg et al., 2014; Carroll et al., 2013; Yun et al., 2014; Tzanakaki et al., 2014; Garcia-Albea, 2014; Groskreutz, 2015; and Hood, 2015; Lerman, 2016; Kouo and Egel, 2016; and Walker, 2017; Hamdan, 2018; and Waldvogel et al., n.d.).

PA developed sustained eye contact as a result of the DTT program. The development of this non-verbal social communication skills skill is generally supported by the findings of (Devlin and Harber 2004; Martins and Harris, 2006; Jones et al., 2006; Kasari, 2006; Lafasakis and Sturmey, 2007; Rocha et al., 2007; Jennett et al., 2008; Miles and Wilder et al., 2009; Mosier, 2011; Nosik and Williams, 2011; Lerman, 2013; Nosik et al., 2013; Carbone et al., 2013; Krstovska-Guerrero and Jones, 2013; Krstovska-Guerrero and Jones, 2013; Shillingsburg et al., 2014; Carroll et al., 2013; Lerman, 2016; and Hamdan, 2018). It shows that developing eye contact within the framework of the DTT program among the segment of the population with ASD remained the target of the researchers in the past on the one hand. On the other hand, the particular perspective in which the current study was carried out across four comparative components to investigate the optimal efficacy of the DTT program in Pakistani society was not supported by the literature.

PB developed understanding/recognition/using affect due to the DTT program. The development of this non-verbal social communication skills is generally supported by the findings of (Gena, 2005; DeQuinzio, 2007; Downs and Strand, 2008; Kouo and Egel, 2016; and Walker, 2017). This shows that developing understanding/recognition/using affect within the framework of DTT program among the segment of population with ASD remained the target of the researchers in the past on one hand. On other hand, the particular perspective in which the current study was carried out across four comparative components to investigate the optimal efficacy of DTT program in Pakistani society was not supported by literature.

Likewise, PB developed gestures as a result of the DTT program. The development of this non-verbal social communication skills skill is supported by the findings of (Buffington, 1998; Ingersoll et al., 2007; and Waldvogel et al., n.d.). Only two studies mentioned here targeted impaired gestures among the segment of the population with ASD. This shows that developing gestures within the framework of the DTT program among the segment of the population with ASD was not the target of the researchers in the past. That is why; the particular perspective in which the current study was carried out across four comparative components to investigate the optimal efficacy of the DTT program in Pakistani society was not supported by the literature.

Conclusions

The effectiveness of implementing the DTT program resulted in synchronizing communication skills among children with ASD in the district Toba Tek Singh of the Punjab province, Pakistan, across all the treatment phases of the program with the insignificant difference of achievement for all the participants of the study investigated by tau-u analysis. Therefore, the DTT program proved to be effective in Pakistani society. Generally, it reserved no additional cost else than existed cost consumed across the designed contexts such as: b) administering treatment inside the classroom context under no error correction/signaling no technique, c) administering treatment inside the classroom context under error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique, d) administering treatment inside the autism friendly training room under no error correction/signaling no technique (temporarily designed context) and e) administering treatment inside the autism friendly training room under error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (temporarily designed context) for PA; b) administering treatment inside the autism friendly training room under regressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to no error correction/signaling no technique (temporarily designed context), c) administering treatment inside the autism friendly training room under progressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (temporarily designed context), d) administering treatment inside the classroom context under regressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to no error

correction/signaling no technique and e) administering treatment inside the classroom context under progressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique for PB inside the GSECG. On the other hand, it indicates the usefulness of the DTT program without making any changes in delivering trials.

The above closure of findings finally led the researchers to conclude that administering treatment inside the autism-friendly training room under error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique (temporarily designed context) and administering treatment inside the classroom context under progressive inter-trial interval technique in addition to error correction/immediate corrective feedback technique reserves efficacy for PA and PB respectively more than administering other treatments across other contexts.

Implications

This study will strengthen the non-verbal communication skills of children with ASD.

Special educationists will equip this segment of the population inside the premises of government special education institutions to address their social areas of deficits and other related complaints across the province of Punjab, Pakistan.

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Author Information

Hina Hadayat Ali

Ph. D Scholar, Special Education, Institute of Special Education, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Dr. Hina Fazil

Assistant Professor, Institute of Special Education, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.
